

TOUGHENING OF CERAMICS BY METAL FIBER REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

An Al/Al₂O₃ composite material was made with the aluminum existing in the form of regularly spaced fibers orientated perpendicular to the cracking plane in a compact tension sample. Crack resistance curves were determined for the composite material and the matrix material. The stress-crack opening (p-u) behaviour of the fibers was then determined by slicing the compact tension samples. The rising section of the p-u curve was found to agree well with a slip line dislocation model. Predictions were then made of the composite R-curves by combining the R-curve behaviour of the matrix material and the crack-tip shielding effects of the ductile ligaments. The R-curve predictions were found to agree well with the experimental data.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic materials exhibit many attractive properties for structural applications including high strength, exceptional wear resistance, good corrosion resistance and in many cases suitability for use in high temperature applications. Low fracture toughness limits the applicability of ceramic materials, however, leading to high flaw sensitivity and low structural reliability relative to other engineering materials, especially metals. Toughness improvement is therefore one of the main thrusts of present research in ceramic material design.

The inclusion of a ductile phase into a brittle matrix is one route that has been explored in order to improve toughness. One type of structure includes tungsten carbide reinforced with a ductile cobalt phase[1] and intermetallic composites such as TiAl/Nb[2] where the ductile phase exists essentially as islands in the brittle matrix. A more interesting microstructure involves the inclusion of the ductile phase in the form of an interpenetrating network with the ceramic matrix. Examples of this structure are Al₂O₃ reinforced with Al or Cu ductile phases[3,4].

In this work a ceramic matrix composite was developed which involved the inclusion of the ductile phase in the form of regularly orientated fibers. This structure has the advantage of orientating various mechanical properties, as has been considered with laminate structures. Essentially however, the material was developed as a model experiment to study the various processes associated with the interpenetrating network microstructure. In particular, information is required about the deformation processes of the ductile phase and their effect upon material toughening and also the fracture mode of the ductile phase.

The material used was an Al/Al₂O₃ composite. The load extension behaviour of the ductile phase was studied *in situ* and fracture toughness measurements made of the composite and matrix material. Toughness values of the composite were found to be significantly higher than the matrix material alone. Fractography was made of the fracture surfaces to enable further understanding of the fracture mode. Finally results were analyzed by considering the

mechanical deformation processes of the ductile phase and its toughening effect. The theoretical model was found to agree well with experimental results.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

MATERIAL

The material used was an alumina matrix reinforced with aluminum fibers. The ceramic matrix was prepared by immersing 150 regularly spaced polymer fibers within an alumina slip. This was undertaken using a purpose built device. Following drying of the slip, the polymer fibers were removed and the alumina sintered. The aluminum was then infiltrated using a specially designed gas pressure infiltration furnace. In the final structure the fibers had an average diameter of $350\ \mu\text{m}$ and were orientated according to Fig.1. A sample was also made using unreinforced alumina to compare the properties of the reinforced versus unreinforced alumina.

Figure 1. Fracture surface showing fiber orientation

Three compact tension (CT) samples were then prepared according to ASTM E-399-83[5], two of dimensions $50\times 48\times 2\ \text{mm}$ (Samples 1&2) and the third $25\times 24\times 2\ \text{mm}$ (Sample 3). The fibers were orientated perpendicular to the cracking direction. An alumina CT sample of $50\times 48\times 2\ \text{mm}$ was also prepared.

MECHANICAL TESTING

Crack resistance curves from all samples were made under an optical microscope with video attachment using an *in situ* loading device and stress intensity factors calculated according to the standard[5]. Following the crack resistance curve measurement of Sample 3 the loading fixture was placed inside the SEM and the crack opening displacements (CODs) measured at regular intervals from the crack tip, with special consideration made to the first 5 mm of crack extension.

Following the crack resistance curve testing a glass plate was glued to the side of the CT sample and the entire piece sliced in the direction of the fibers with each strip approximately 4 mm wide containing 12 fibers. The glass was then removed and the slice placed in a tensile testing machine with an extensometer attached at each side of the crack. The sample was loaded under tension and applied load and displacement simultaneously recorded. The load was then converted to stress using the cross-sectional area of the fibers and a stress versus displacement (p-u) curve obtained with the displacement, u, here being analogous to crack opening, u, in the COD observations.

Following fracture the fracture surfaces were observed in a SEM.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The three crack resistance curves from the composites and the one from the alumina sample can be seen in Fig.2. In the initial stages the curves for the composites are the same as those for the unreinforced alumina. This is because there is a section of initial crack extension before the crack encounters the first bridge (maximum 350 μm), and then before the ligament extends enough to exert significant closure forces relative to those caused by the grain bridges in the alumina. At a crack extension, c , of 1 mm a clear divergence between the two materials can be seen. The alumina R-curve plateaus at 3.4 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ at $c=1.4$ mm but at this stage the Al ligaments exert significant closure stresses causing further rise in the R-curve of the composite. The intrinsic toughness of the composite, K_0 , is therefore equal to K_0 of the alumina ~ 2 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$.

Figure 2. Experimental and Theoretical Crack Resistance Curves

The composite R-curves display a clear stepwise behaviour as they rise. This is due to the fact that as the crack extends it encounters a ductile bridging ligament which exerts an increasing closure force as the crack grows around it. This is signified by the steeply rising sections in the R-curve. Once the crack is past this bridge the rate of increase of closure force decreases dramatically, signified by a flatter region in the R-curve, until the next bridge is encountered and the process repeated. The composite R-curves also rise steadily with no sign of plateauing. If anything they appear to have an increasing steepness however this is most probably due to irregularities in the stress intensity factor calculations as a result of the large crack extensions (>5 mm) involved.

The results of the COD measurements on Sample 3 can be seen in Fig.3. Over the initial 5 mm from the crack tip the ductile ligaments exert significant closure forces and CODs are held to less than 1 μm . Further from the crack tip however relatively large crack extensions occur where no bridging ligaments exist.

Fig.4 shows a sample of two of the p-u curves that were obtained. Both curves show an initial steep rise to a peak stress of approximately 70 MPa at a crack extension, $2u_0$, of 20 μm . The stress then decreases exponentially, an indication of necking behaviour, to fracture at $2u_0=250$

or 450 μm respectively for each curve. Theoretically all the p-u curves should be identical but small amounts of delamination near the fracture plane may cause discrepancies.

Figure 3. Crack opening displacements for composite and glass control material

Figure 4. Stress-displacement ($p-u$) curves for ligaments

Figure 5. Fracture surfaces of (a) fully constrained and (b) partially constrained ligaments. Note matrix fracture at lower side and void in (b).

Fig.5(a)&(b) shows two fractured ligaments. In both cases fracture is by ductile tearing originating most probably from a void. In Fig.5(a) the ligament appears to have necked somewhat prior to failure. A small amount of fracture of the matrix close to the ligament/matrix interface can be seen. This would reduce the constraint, though minimally, on the fiber leading to the more ductile extension, i.e. with necking, as for example seen in Curve 2 in Fig.4 where $2u_0=450 \mu\text{m}$. In Fig.5(b) no evidence of processes which would reduce constraint can be seen, causing a smaller value of u_0 .

THEORETICAL MODELING

STRESS - DISPLACEMENT (p-u) CURVE

It can be seen in Fig.4 that the p-u curve contains two distinct sections separated by $2u_0$, the extension at peak stress. As the CODs involved in this work are significantly less than $2u_0$, as seen in Fig.3, only the first steeply rising section of the p-u curve need be considered. The basis of this section of the model is based upon work by Ashby et al[6] who considered a similar situation where a single ductile ligament, constrained within a glass tube, was loaded under tension. The initial rise of the p-u curve is considered to occur by a process of dislocation pile up along slip lines.

On initial loading a stress concentration in the fiber occurs where the crack plane and fiber intersect. Dislocations nucleate at the interface between the crack and the fiber and propagate across the fiber at an angle of 45° to the crack plane where shear stress is greatest. The dislocations then pile up at the fiber/matrix interface. A shear stress, τ , compresses a pile up of n dislocations of Burgers vector, b , into a length, L , according to [7]:

$$nb = \frac{\pi \tau L}{G} \quad (1)$$

As maximum τ occurs in slip planes at 45° to the tensile axis then:

$$L = 2\sqrt{2} d_0 \quad (2)$$

The initial rising part of the p-u curve reaches a peak at maximum dislocation pile up, i.e. $2u_0 = \sqrt{2}nb$. Replacing τ by $\sigma/2$ and G by $3E/8$, where σ is the maximum tensile stress at $2u_0$ and E the Youngs Modulus gives:

$$\sigma = \frac{3E \cdot 2u_0}{8\pi d_0} \quad (3)$$

as d_0 is constant and the initial rising part of the curve linear it is possible to replace $2u_0$ with $2u$ to give:

$$p(u) = \frac{3E \cdot 2u}{8\pi d_0} \quad (4)$$

COD VERSUS DISTANCE FROM CRACK TIP

Fig.6 shows the coordinate system used in this section of the model and also for the later R-curve predictions. a is the total crack length and c the crack extension during testing which is also the length over which ductile ligament bridging occurs.

Near crack tip CODs, $2u$, in an isotropic elastic material may be related to the distance from the crack tip by [8]:

$$2u(x, a) = \sqrt{\frac{8}{\pi}} \frac{K_{tip}}{E'} \sqrt{a-x} \quad (5)$$

K_{tip} is the stress intensity factor at the crack tip and for a crack just prior to crack extension in inert conditions and is equal to the intrinsic toughness of the material, K_0 .

Figure 6. Coordinate system used for crack extension modeling

CRACK RESISTANCE CURVE

In the Al/Al₂O₃ composite there are two contributions to the crack extension toughening: that which may be attributed to crack bridging by the alumina grains as a result of typical intergranular crack growth and that resulting from closure stresses exerted by the aluminum fibers as they extend. As it is the aim of this work to determine the effect of the aluminum fibers a complicated frictional model of grain bridging will not be made but a simplified, empirically based representation used[9]:

$$K_s^{Al_2O_3} = K_0 \left(\frac{c}{c_0} \right)^b - K_0 \quad (6)$$

where b and c_0 are constants determined from experimental data.

The crack-tip shielding effect of the aluminum fibers may be determined by equating the integral[10]:

$$K_s^{Al} = \int_{a-c}^a h(x, a) p(x, a) dx \quad (7)$$

where h is a weight function according to the specimen geometry of the form:

$$h = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi a}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x/a}} \left[1 + \sum_{(\nu, \mu)} \frac{A_{\nu\mu} \alpha^\mu}{(1-\alpha)^\mu} \left(1 - x/a \right)^{\nu+1} \right] \quad (8)$$

where $\alpha=a/W$ and the coefficients $A_{\nu\mu}$ for a compact tension sample, as used in the experimental section of this work, given in the Appendix.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The advantages of using ductile metal fibers tightly bonded within the matrix are twofold: first the tight bonding results in a high level of stress for initial yielding and hence crack opening, and second, once yielding has occurred the fiber deforms in a ductile manner requiring further energy and causing crack closure forces well behind the crack tip.

Close inspection reveals that Eqn (4) agrees well with the experimental p-u curve in the initial rising section. The peak stress in the experimental p-u curve is in the order of twice the flow stress, $\sigma_0=40$ MPa, for pure aluminum. Theoretically for perfect bonding at the Al/Al₂O₃ interface the peak in the p-u curve should be in the order of 5-6 times σ_0 for the value of u_0 obtained during testing. The rising part of the p-u curve also shows slight non-linear behaviour just prior to peaking. This would be caused by delamination near the crack plane as the load increased, reducing constraint on the fiber. Concurrently this would explain the lower than expected levels of peak stress, different post yield behaviour and different values of u_0 as seen in comparing Curves 1 and 2. Fig.3 shows that at the CODs obtained during R-curve testing

are less than 15 μm , where the p - u curve behaviour is still clearly linear and in agreement with the slip line dislocation model. Application of Eqn (4) to this situation is therefore valid.

Fig.3 shows a comparison between the experimental data and Eqn (5). While Eqn (5) presents a reasonable fit to the experimental data in the near tip region and where crack bridging occurs i.e. $x < 5$ mm, closer examination indicates that it underestimates $u(x)$ at $x < 2$ mm and progressively overestimates $u(x)$ as x increases. The situation here is outside the bounds prescribed for use of Eqn (5): Firstly, the equation is strictly for an isotropic material, which our composite is not, in regions near the crack tip. In relation to the microstructure of the material crack extensions in the order of millimeters are not 'near tip' features. Secondly, Eqn (5) does not consider any crack closure forces which are significant in this case as indicated by the R-curve data. A comparative experiment with a model material, glass, which fills the conditions for the application of Eqn (5) is shown in Fig.3 verifying the inapplicability of Eqn (5) to this case.

Therefore an empirical power law fit is made of the experimental data of the form:

$$2u(x, a) = B(a - x)^m \quad (9)$$

where B and m are constants.

Noting that because the fibers are regularly located along the crack path with gaps in between $p(x)$ is a rectangular type function, Eqn (4) is then equated with Eqn (9) to give:

$$p(x, a) = \frac{3EB(a - x)^m}{4\pi d_0} \quad \text{fiber at } x$$

$$p(x, a) = 0 \quad \text{no fiber at } x \quad (10)$$

Eqn (7) is then integrated for various crack extensions, c , to obtain the contribution of the ductile ligaments to overall crack-tip shielding. The applied stress intensity factor, K_A , may be calculated according to:

$$K_A = K_0 + K_s^{Al_2O_3} + K_s^{Al} \quad (11)$$

and compared with the experimental R-curves in Fig.2.

The modeled curves show close agreement with the experimental data: the stepwise behaviour in the experimental data is explained in terms of the rectangular $p(x)$ function and the upward rise towards the end of the curve, especially in Sample 3 by the weight function, h . In a specimen of infinite dimensions the R-curves will continue to rise, essentially linearly until $u(a-c) = u_0$ and not plateau until $u(a-c) = u^*$. Assuming that $u(x)$ follows the behaviour estimated in Eqn (9) the COD would become equal to $2u_0$ at $c = 117m!$ Fiber breakage in crack extension of this type is therefore not a feasible occurrence in this type of material.

One of the aims of this work was to act as a model experiment for the interpenetrating network Al/Al_2O_3 structure. The interpenetrating network structure represents many small diameter ductile ligaments. Significantly, mechanical constraint of the ductile phase is much higher in the interpenetrating network microstructure, resulting in higher bridging stresses prior to ligament yield but conversely, shorter ligament failure extensions. Consideration of Eqn (4) quickly shows that smaller diameter fibers will result in a far more steeply rising initial section of the p - u curve. Considering the 'smear-like' effect of the ductile ligament closure stresses resulting from many irregularly located and orientated ligaments the $p(x)$ function should not show a stepwise behaviour.

These factors result in materials with steeply rising R-curves. Therefore stress intensity factors for the propagation of critical flaws in an interpenetrating network structure are much higher than for the pure matrix material and crack extension toughening is of secondary importance.

CONCLUSIONS

A number of points may be concluded from this work:

- (1) The inclusion of ductile aluminum fibers significantly increased the toughness of the alumina matrix.
- (2) Constraint of the fibers and their adhesion to the matrix effect the closure stresses that they exert upon an open crack.
- (3) The inclusion of the fibers produced a stepwise, slowly rising R-curve. The toughening effect of the alumina grain bridges becomes superseded by the ductile ligaments after a relatively short amount of crack extension.

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APPENDIX

Coefficients, $A_{v\mu}$, in Eqn (8):

v	$\mu = 0$	1	2	3	4
0	2.673	-8.604	20.621	-14.635	0.477
1	-3.557	24.9726	-53.398	50.707	-11.837
2	1.230	-8.411	16.957	-12.157	-0.940
3	-0.157	0.954	-1.284	-0.393	1.655